

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON THE PROGRESSIVE CRUSHING OF COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A study of the moisture absorption properties of a glass-reinforced epoxy composite has been made, and the effect of moisture on energy absorption by progressive crushing investigated. The study has involved quasi-static, axial crushing of glass-reinforced epoxy resin tubes, preconditioned by total immersion in distilled water over a temperature range of 20°C to 80°C. Degradation of the progressive crush stress has been examined, changes in crush mode identified and comparisons drawn with the moisture induced variations in mechanical properties and previously identified energy absorbing mechanisms.

KEYWORDS: Environmental effect; matrix, epoxy; friction; woven; progressive crushing.

1. INTRODUCTION

In common with engineering materials in general, polymer composite materials interact with the environments in which they are used. Because of their expanding use in structures where mechanical performance is critical, the nature of any physical and chemical interactions, and the resulting influence on material properties, must be assessed. Indeed, there remains considerable uncertainty amongst many engineers and scientists as to the response of composites when exposed to complex loading conditions and environmental exposure. Hence, design safety factors for these versatile materials are generally high, and the superior specific strength and stiffness properties are rarely used to their full advantage. Until such problems are satisfactorily addressed, polymer matrix composites may continue to be under-exploited. It has been widely reported that polymer matrix composite materials are excellent energy absorbers when suitably triggered axisymmetric tubes are axially crushed (1). Much data has been produced concerning the material, geometrical and testing parameters which influence the levels of energy absorption attainable by progressive crushing. The influence of environmental factors on the progressive crushing of polymer matrix composite structures has to date been limited to investigations of the effect of testing temperature (2). It has been identified that the

effect of long term exposure to moisture on polymers and polymer matrix composites is of considerable importance (3). This study attempts to investigate systematically the effects of absorbed moisture on the progressive crushing behaviour of glass-fibre reinforced epoxy tubes, and relate any changes to environmentally induced variations in material properties and previously identified energy absorbing mechanisms.

2. MATERIALS

The material examined was a fine, plain weave E glass-cloth reinforced epoxy resin (Ciba-Geigy 7065N75). Tubular sections of 50 mm internal diameter and 55 mm external diameter were manufactured by rolling of pre-preg, such that the warp and weft directions of the cloth were parallel and perpendicular to the axis of the tube. Curing was carried out at 135°C for 2.5 hours and the tubes then centreless ground so that a wall thickness of 2.5 mm was attained. Tubes were subjected to quality control with respect to their dimensional tolerance and eccentricity, and were ensured to comply with British Standard 6128. Flat laminate of the same material was used for the production of mechanical test coupons, this being produced by consolidation of pre-preg in pressurised steel moulds.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Tube Crush Tests Tube lengths approximately 110 mm long were cut using a water lubricated, diamond coated, cut-off wheel. A double 30° chamfer was then cut onto one end of the tube, ensuring that the chamfer apex was in the mid-wall position. Tubes were then cleaned in a detergent solution, rinsed in water, dried with absorbent tissue and finally placed in a drying cabinet in which a constant temperature of 50±0.5°C was maintained. Drying was carried out until no further weight loss was measurable with a balance having an accuracy of 0.01g. Tube end surfaces were sealed using silicone rubber and their dry weight recorded to an accuracy of 0.01g. Dried specimens were then immersed in distilled water at temperatures of 20±2°C, 40±0.5°C, 60±0.5°C and 80±0.5°C using thermostatically controlled baths. At various time intervals, tubes were removed from their precondition environments, dried using absorbent tissue, and weighed so that their moisture absorbing characteristics could be monitored. Once the specimens had reached the desired moisture content they were dried and allowed to attain ambient temperature, and their wall thicknesses measured so that a mean figure could be determined. Tubes were axially compressed over a total distance of 50mm, at a rate of 2mm/s between hardened steel platens, using a 200kN capacity, servo-hydraulic testing facility. During crushing, load - displacement traces were recorded and the nature of the crush process observed. Crushed specimens were finally mounted in a cold curing resin and sections of the crush zone removed for optical microscopy.

3.2 Crush Front-Platen Friction Tests An assessment of the coefficient of friction at the crush platen - composite interface was carried out using an experimental technique developed

by Fairfull (4). Tube specimens approximately 160 mm long were prepared in the same manner as those used in the axial compression tests. After chamfering, holes were drilled through the tubes at the opposite end to the chamfer, so that a steel pin and collars could be used to secure specimens to the torsion apparatus (figure 1). Specimens were preconditioned in the same manner as the tubes used for simple axial crushing tests. The coefficient of sliding friction was assessed using a combined torsion - compression testing facility, with a torque capacity of 2kNm and an axial load capacity of 100kN. Tubes were placed on the loading spigot as shown in figure 1 and prevented from rotating using collars which bound tightly onto the outer surface of the tubes.

FIGURE 1. Schematic showing combined torsion/compression rig used for measuring crush front - platen friction coefficient.

Tubes were then crushed axially against a hardened steel platen at a rate of 2mm/s, over a distance of 20mm and the load - displacement trace recorded. The axial load applied to the crushed specimen was then reduced to 10kN, a rotation of 4.7 degrees/s applied over a rotation of 50° and the resultant torque - rotation trace obtained. This value of rotation rate was selected since it corresponded to a displacement rate of 2mm/s at the tube mid wall in axial crushing. The loading process was then repeated with the same precrushed tube, increasing the axial load in steps of 5kN and recording the resultant torques, until axial crushing was initiated under combined torsional and axial loads. From the graphs of torque versus displacement for each value of axial load, the coefficient of crush front - platen friction was found. This was calculated using the equation.

$$\mu = \frac{\tau}{P \bar{r}}$$

where τ = torque, P = axial load, \bar{r} = mean tube radius, μ = coefficient of friction.

3.3 Tensile Tests Tensile tests were carried out in accordance with the UK Composites Research Advisory Group, (CRAG), recommendations (5). Specimens were cut from 2.5mm thick sheet such that the warp or weft fibres in the woven cloth were parallel to the edges of the specimen. End tabs of the same material were applied to half of the specimens using a room temperature curing epoxy adhesive, and again, all specimens were dried at a temperature of 50°C. Specimens were then paired, ie. one tabbed and one untabbed coupon. Following

edge sealing with silicone rubber and weighing, they were immersed in the same water baths as the tubular specimens. In order to monitor moisture uptake of the composite in the gauge length only, the untabbed specimens were removed, dried and weighed at regular intervals. Once the required moisture content had been achieved, the tabbed specimens were removed, strain gauges applied and then tested in tension at a displacement rate of 2 mm/min using a 100 kN capacity screw driven testing machine. Specimens were tested to failure and load - displacement and load - strain curves recorded.

3.4 Interlaminar Shear Strength Tests The method chosen for measuring the interlaminar shear strength, (ILSS), of the material was once again that recommended by CRAG, ie. the short beam, three point bend test. Specimens of dimensions 20mm x 10 mm x 2.2mm were cut from flat plate such that one of the sets of woven threads was parallel with the edges of the specimen. Support rollers of 6mm diameter were spaced 11 mm apart and the specimen loaded with a centrally located, 6mm diameter roller, at a displacement rate of 1mm/min. Specimen preconditioning was performed as described previously, and the ILSS calculated from:

$$ILSS = 0.75 P / Wt$$

where P is the peak load, W is the specimen width and t is the specimen thickness.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Moisture Absorption and Axial Crushing The weight gain of tubes preconditioned at the various temperatures is shown in figure 2 . Each data point corresponds to the average value calculated from the absorption of ten tubes.

FIGURE 2. Curves showing weight gain due to absorption of moisture in tubes preconditioned at various temperatures.

In most cases, individual tubes did not deviate from this mean value by more than 1 to 2% however, some specimens showed absorption at a very fast rate, and these were excluded from the study. Typical load displacement traces for tubes with different moisture contents are shown in figure 3. The mean crush load and the serration amplitude decreased with increasing moisture content.

FIGURE 3. Load-displacement traces for preconditioned, axially crushed tubes.
 A: 0.48% weight gain, preconditioned at 20°C for 1800 hours.
 B: 0.79% weight gain, preconditioned at 40°C for 2184 hours.
 C: 3.55% weight gain, preconditioned at 80°C for 1100 hours.

Schematics of crush zone micrographs and plan views of tubes showing changes in crush mode are shown in figures 4, 5 and 6. Specimens with up to 1% weight gain were found to crush by the fragmentation mode. Above this value, the crushing mode changed to one of frond splaying, with increasing moisture content leading to smoother surfaces on the lower frond surfaces and less evidence of fracture within the fronds. Changes in the number of radial fronds and even the occurrence of failure by processes other than progressive crushing from the chamfered end were seen. It was found that once the splaying mode of progressive crushing had been achieved, ie above about 1% moisture, then the number of fronds reduced from 11 at about 1% to only 8 or 9 at 7% (figure 5 & 6, plan view).

The variation in crush stress with absorbed moisture is shown in figure 7. There is a marked decrease in crush stress with the first 3% absorbed moisture, after which the crush stress remained reasonably constant.

FIGURE 7. Variation of crush stress with % weight gain for preconditioned tubes.

4.2 Tube Friction Test The variation of friction coefficient with absorbed moisture is shown in figure 8. Tubes tested with the higher values of absorbed moisture exhibited a stick - slip type of friction with the crush platen and this was manifested by both serrations on the torque-displacement curves and by the emission of considerable noise during the tests. There is a marked increase in the coefficient of sliding friction with moisture content which is in

agreement with other published work on the influence of moisture on the tribological properties of polymer composites (6).

FIGURE 8. Variation of crush front-platen friction coefficient with % weight gain.

It was found that during combined axial and torsional loading, the axial progressive crush stress was lower than that found under axial loading alone. This prevented measurements of torque and therefore friction coefficient at axial loads equal to or close to the axial progressive crush load. Nonetheless, the coefficient of friction did not appear to be greatly influenced by the value of the axial load, and hence it was assumed that the value for the friction coefficient was the same at the maximum combined axial and torsional crush load as at the crush load under axial load only.

4.3 Tensile Tests The variation of tensile strength with weight gain is shown in figure 9. Similarly to the crush stress variation, the tensile strength reduced dramatically over the first 1.5% weight gain, after which a stable level was reached. Specimens conditioned at 60° and 80°C showed considerable surface attack, cracking and discolouration, as well as exhibiting contrasting fracture surfaces to the dry and low water content specimens. Surface roughening due to the leaching of resin was seen on the specimens exposed at 60 and 80°C, together with a change in colour of the resin from the translucent pale green in the dry state, to an opaque orange - yellow in the conditioned state. Those specimens exposed at 80°C were also found to slowly emit ammonia during preconditioning due to the hydrolysis of excess curing agent.

4.4 Interlaminar Shear Tests The results of the three point bend, ILSS tests are shown in figure 10. Once again, there was an initial rapid degradative effect, followed by a gradual levelling off to a stable strength value. A number of important points must however be noted in

the interpretation of these results. In those samples which had high weight gains following preconditioning at the higher temperatures, it was not clear that the failure was by interlaminar shear. When samples were examined by optical microscopy, interlaminar shear cracks were not readily visible, and in some specimens, there was evidence of tensile failure in the lower plies of the short beam.

FIGURE 9. Variation of tensile strength with % weight gain.

FIGURE 10. Variation of interlaminar shear strength with % weight gain.

5. DISCUSSION

The effect of moisture on the progressive crushing of glass cloth reinforced epoxy tubes has been shown to be of considerable importance, there being a substantial decrease in the crush stress with absorbed moisture. The effect of absorbed moisture on the tensile and interlaminar shear strengths however, appears to be much greater than the degradative effect on the progressive crush stress. The friction experiment may however go some way to explaining why the crush stress is not affected to the same degree as the measured strength properties. It has been generally accepted that friction within the crush zone and at the crush zone / platen interface makes a considerable contribution to the energy absorbing process when tubes are axially crushed (4). Hence, it is not wholly surprising that if the friction coefficient increases with absorbed moisture, the progressive crush stress is not degraded by as much as the strength properties of the material. The changes in the mechanical properties nonetheless provide an insight into the factors which bring about changes in the crush zone morphology. Consider for example the changes observed between the specimens shown in figures 5 and 6. The most obvious difference between the two specimens is the decrease in the extent of fracture within the fronds, and the decrease in the actual number of fronds. These phenomena must indicate that the material has become less susceptible to trans-ply fracture and more ductile as the moisture content increased. The ability to form splaying fronds may be a result of the decrease in the interlaminar shear strength, since as the tube wall material is forced around the debris wedge, individual plies are each forced through a different radius of curvature and hence there is shear between individual layers. If the interlaminar shear strength is sufficiently low, as is the case at the higher moisture contents, then the plies become decoupled at or near the debris wedge, preventing trans-ply fracture and allowing the smooth flow of fronds. There is considerable evidence of de-ply in the fronds of the high moisture content tubes, and this is particularly evident in the internally deflected fronds which are forced through a smaller radius of curvature than the external fronds. Clearly, many parallels can be drawn between the changes in mechanical properties and the changes in crush mode and hence, changes in energy absorption. However, this does not imply that there are easily identifiable relationships between the mechanical properties and the value of progressive crush stress. An attempt to produce simple equations relating the basic property changes to energy absorption would be simplistic and at this stage erroneous. Nonetheless, this study has indicated that moisture induced changes in crush mode can in some way be described by considering the moisture induced variations in mechanical properties and energy absorbing mechanisms such as friction.

6. REFERENCES

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